

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377477>

UDK 623.54

**THE EFFECT OF SABOT STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS
ON MINIMUM REQUIRED MUZZLE VELOCITY
FOR 7.62MM PISTOL ARMOR-PIERCING BULLETS**

Q.T. Nguyen,

H.M. Nguyen,

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor,

X.S. Bui,

Candidate of Technical Sciences,
Le Quy Don Technical University

Annotation: In this study, the effect of the number and length of grooves on sabot of armor-piercing bullets fired from pistols with caliber of 7.62mm on their minimum required muzzle velocity was investigated. The Ansys Workbench Explicit Dynamics module was applied for this study. The material of sabot is unfilled thermoplastic polymer PEEK. The study has shown that the number and the length of grooves of sabot has great effect on the bullet minimum required muzzle velocity so that the bullet's core reliably leaves the sabot after exiting the muzzle. The results obtained in this work can be used in designing sabot armor-piercing bullets fired from 7.62mm pistols.

Keywords: armor piercing bullets, sabot separation, PEEK polymer, 7.62mm caliber pistol, Ansys Workbench, Explicit Dynamics, numerical simulation

ВЛИЯНИЕ КОНСТРУКТИВНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ПОДУШКА НА МИНИМАЛЬНУЮ НЕОБХОДИМУЮ НАЧАЛЬНУЮ СКОРОСТЬ ДЛЯ 7,62-ММ ПИСТОЛЕТНЫХ БРОНЕБОЙНЫХ ПУЛЕЙ

**К.Т. Нгуен,
Х.М. Нгуен,**

к.т.н., доц.

С.С. Буй,

к.т.н.,

Технический университет Ле Куи Дона

Аннотация: В данной работе исследовано влияние количества и длины нарезов на подкалиберных бронебойных пулях, выпущенных из пистолетов калибра 7,62 мм, на их минимально необходимую начальную скорость. Для этого исследования был применен модуль Ansys Workbench Explicit Dynamics. Материал сабо – ненаполненный термопластичный полимер ПEEK. Исследование показало, что количество и длина нарезов поддона оказывает большое влияние на минимально необходимую начальную скорость пули, чтобы сердечник пули после выхода из дульного среза надежно покидал поддон. Результаты, полученные в данной работе, могут быть использованы при конструировании подкалиберных бронебойных пуль, стреляющих из пистолетов калибра 7,62 мм.

Ключевые слова: бронебойные пули, подкалиберное разделение, полимер ПEEK, пистолет калибра 7,62 мм, Ansys Workbench, Explicit Dynamics, численное моделирование

Introduction. Currently, along with significant achievements in the field of new materials, the bulletproof armor of the armed forces in the world is increasingly improved and is better able to protect soldiers. Moreover, combat vehicles are also perfected and equipped with thicker armor protection. That fact poses an urgent requirement to improve the piercing performance of bullets. One of the most promising ways to improve the penetrating power of the ammunition is to use sabot bullets, such as M903 SLAP (Fig. 1). This bullet consists of a sabot made of

lightweight materials and a penetrator made of hard high-density metals [1]. On the sabots, there are weakened grooves (3 or 4) to concentrate stress. After exiting the barrel, under the action of centrifugal force, the sabot breaks into pieces; the penetrator escapes the sabot and continues to move towards the target (Fig. 2) [2]. Due to its lighter weight than conventional bullets, the sabot bullets have very high velocity. Moreover, the penetrator's diameter is also smaller than the conventional bullet diameter, thus reducing the loss of kinetic energy due to aerodynamic drag. However, in order for the sabot to be able to break into pieces after exiting the gun barrel, the bullet has to obtain a sufficient initial spinning velocity. For a certain gun, the bullet's initial spinning velocity definitely relates with its muzzle velocity. Therefore, in order for the sabot to be discarded after leaving the gun barrel, the bullet ought to possess a certain minimum required muzzle velocity. For a sabot of certain dimensions and material, the minimum required muzzle velocity can vary depending on the number and length of the grooves.

Figure 1 – The bullet and complete cartridge of 12.7x99mm M903 SLAP

Figure 2 – The separation of sabot and penetrator of M903 SLAP

Figure 4 – Finite element model of the sabot

The sabot material has to be strong enough to withstand high impact loading while being launched from a rifled gun barrel, but brittle enough to fragment nearly immediately upon leaving the gun muzzle due to centrifugal forces. One of the suitable materials for sabot is unfilled PEEK (Polyetheretherketone) polymer [4]. PEEK is a lightweight, chemical resistant, high-performance engineering plastic with outstanding mechanical strength and dimensional stability. The material properties of sabot necessary for simulation were obtained from [5] and listed in the Table 1.

Table 1 – The material properties of sabot

Material parameters	PEEK
Density, kg/m^3	1300
Specific heat, J/(kgC)	1340
Young's Modulus, MPa	3600
Poisson's ratio	0.4
<i>Constitutive model: Johnson Cook</i>	
Yield stress, MPa	132
Strain hardening constant, MPa	10
Strain hardening coefficient	1.2

Material parameters	PEEK
Strengthening coefficient of strain rate	0.034
Thermal softening coefficient	0.7
Melting temperature, °C	340
<i>Failure model: Stress failure</i>	
Maximum tensile stress, MPa	115
Maximum compressive stress, MPa	130

The numerical simulation used bullet’s spinning velocity at the muzzle as initial condition. However, in the science of ballistics, the bullet’s muzzle velocity is used as a main input parameter for the fundamental problems of interior and exterior ballistics. In this study the bullet’s spinning velocity at the gun muzzle was calculated through the bullet’s muzzle velocity according to the following formula [6]:

$$\omega_o = \frac{2V_o}{D} \operatorname{tg} \lambda,$$

where ω_o – bullet’s spinning velocity at the muzzle;

V_o – the bullet’s muzzle velocity;

D – the groove diameter of the barrel (in this case, $D = 7.92\text{mm}$);

λ – rifling angle of the barrel (in this case, $\lambda = 5.5^\circ$).

The muzzle velocity of standard bullets fired from pistol is 420m/s [7]. So, for each combination of number and length of sabot, the numerical simulation was carried out with initial spinning velocity calculated through muzzle velocity, which gradually increased from 420 m/s with increment of 5m/s. The simulation process ended as soon as the sabot was able to break into pieces under action of centrifugal force (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 – The sequence of images of sabot deformation after leaving the muzzle (in case of 4 weakened grooves, $h = 2.5\text{mm}$, $V_0 = 585\text{m/s}$)

Results and Discussions. The numerical simulation was carried out for sabots containing 3 and 4 weakened grooves; the uncut portion length was increased from 0mm with increment of 0.5 mm. The dependence of bullet's minimum required muzzle velocity on sabot's structural parameters is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – The dependence of minimum required muzzle velocity on the length of uncut portion of sabot

The simulation results showed that the number of weakened grooves and the length of uncut portion greatly affect the minimum required muzzle velocity. The longer uncut portion is, the greater minimum required muzzle velocity becomes. For the same length of uncut portion, the minimum required muzzle velocity in case of 3 grooves is greater than that in case of 4 grooves. However, the number of grooves has stronger influence with the length of uncut portion smaller than 2 mm. For the uncut portion lengths of 3.5 mm or greater, the minimum required muzzle velocities are quite high (greater than 665 m/s for 4 grooves sabot and greater than 685 m/s for 3 grooves sabot). Therefore, in the range of possible muzzle velocities of pistols, with investigated sabot structure, it is appropriate for sabot to have uncut portion length in the interval from 0mm to 3 mm.

Conclusion. The article has introduced a numerical method to investigate the effect of the number of grooves on sabot and the length of uncut portion on the minimum required muzzle velocities for armor piercing bullets. The obtained results indicated that both these quantities have great influence on the minimum required muzzle velocity of bullets. The method and results presented in this study can be applied in designing armor piercing bullets.

Bibliography

- [1] Fayed A. Tungsten carbide core 12.7x99 mm AP projectiles ballistic behavior against high hardness steel armor. / A. Fayed. // Journal of Physics: Conference Series. – 2022. 12 p.
- [2] 50 Cal Advanced Propellants, Marks Powder. – 2011. 17 p.
- [3] Ansys Workbench Software Tutorial Release – 2020. 192 p.
- [4] Burri J. Releasable sabot for a subcaliber projectile. / J. Burri – 1995. 5 p.
- [5] Garcia-Gonzalez D. Mechanical impact behavior of poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK). / D. Garcia-Gonzalez, A. Rusinek, T. Jankowiak. // Composite structures. – 2015. Vol. 124. 44 p.
- [6] Carlucci D., Jacobson S. Ballistics: Theory and design of guns and ammunition, CRC Press. – 2018. 671 p.
- [7] Shant K. Infantry weapons (in Russian). / K. Shant – 2007. 256 p.

Список литературы

- [1] Файед А. Карбид вольфрамовый сердечник 12,7x99 мм бронебойных снарядов баллистические характеристики против брони из стали высокой твердости. / А. Файед. // Журнал физики: Серия конференций. – 2022. 12 с.
- [2] 50 Cal Advanced Propellents, Marks Powder. – 2011. 17 с.
- [3] Учебное пособие по программному обеспечению Ansys Workbench – 2020. 192 стр.
- [4] Бурри Дж. Съёмный подкалиберный снаряд для подкалиберного снаряда. / Дж. Бурри – 1995. 5 с.
- [5] Гарсия-Гонсалес Д. Механическое воздействие полиэфиркетона (ПЕЕК). / Д. Гарсия-Гонсалес, А. Русинек, Т. Янковяк. // Составные конструкции. – 2015. Том. 124. 44 с.
- [6] Карлуччи Д., Якобсон С. Баллистика: теория и конструкция оружия и боеприпасов, CRC Press. – 2018. 671 с.
- [7] Шант К. Пехотное вооружение. / К. Шант – 2007. 256 с.

© Q.T. Nguyen, H.M. Nguyen, X.S. Bui, 2022

Поступила в редакцию 14.10.2021

Принята к публикации 01.11.2022

Для цитирования:

Nguyen Q.T., Nguyen H.M., Bui X.S. The effect of sabot structural parameters on minimum required muzzle velocity for 7.62mm pistol armor-piercing bullets // Инновационные научные исследования. 2022. № 11-1(23). С. 55-63. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>